

A NEW APPROACH TO DESIGN A REVERSIBLE PROGRAMMABLE READ ONLY MEMORY

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ABSTRACT

Reversible logic has become popular in recent years. In many technologies area, the application of reversible logic is increasing day by day. The main advantages of reversible logic are: there is no information loss and reduction of power occurs in a circuit. In this paper, a new approach to design a Reversible Programmable Read Only Memory (RPROM) has been proposed. For the proposed RPROM, we have also proposed a 4×4 reversible decoder named ITS Decoder gate, which has no garbage output and the quantum cost is lowest than any other existing reversible decoders. We have also proposed a reversible gate named TI gate, which is used in the proposed design. The proposed design is *11.76%* better in terms of total number of gates, *30.90%* better in terms of quantum cost and *47.36%* better in terms of total number of garbage outputs than the best known existing ones. We also proof that the proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate is *12.5%* better than the best known existing ones in terms of quantum cost.

Keywords: Programmable Read Only Memory, Reversible Gate, Decoder, Quantum Cost, Garbage Output and Constant Input.

INTRODUCTION

In the present technology, power excessiveness is one of the key issues. The importance of reversible logic is increasing day by day for its significant property. To get low power devices, reversible logic has become demandable way that is one of the basic reasons. When information becomes lost, then energy is also lost. It happens when an input cannot recover its output and it has been proved by (Landauer, 1961). He also expressed that if a bit of information is lost, then $kT \ln 2$ joules of heat generate; where k is Boltzman's constant of 1.38×10^{-23} J/K and T is absolute temperature. To reduce energy waste, reversible circuits can be used and (Bennet, 1973) showed it. Reversible logic follows one-to-one mapping system followed by input number and output number remains equal. Here, no information is lost and energy dissipation does not occur. (Miller, Maslov & Dueck) proved that if the number of gate increased, then it is not good metric of optimization. But the use of reversible gate can decrease the number of gates, because one output of one gate can be used, if reversible logic supports.

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ROM is used to store the value, which is unchangeable. There is no scope to lose the value, if power is OFF. For this reason, it is nonvolatile. It also provides security because, it is not possible to modify easily. Many research works have been done on reversible memory, but there are a few works that have been done in this area. In recent years, the use of reversible gates is increasing for its major metric of cost optimization.

In this paper, we have proposed a new design of reversible programmable read only memory (RPRM). The existing PROM is irreversible. The proposed RPRM is efficient, because in this RPRM, we have proposed a decoder, which has the lowest quantum cost and no garbage output. We have also proposed a new AND plane and EX-OR plane for decreasing RPRM, in which the number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost are reduced. In this paper, we have also proposed a reversible gate called TI gate.

LITERATURE OVERVIEW

Some basic definitions that will help to understand about reversible gate and logic, garbage output, quantum cost, constant input and read only memory are given below.

1. Reversible Gate

Reversible gate is a gate, which has an equal number of inputs and outputs. Actually, it follows the one-to-one mapping between input vectors and output vectors (Babu, Islam, Chowdhury, & Chowdhury, 2004). Reversible gate has no bit loss. If the inputs are $I_t \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_n\}$, then the outputs will be $O_t \{O_1, O_2, O_3, \dots, O_n\}$.

Fig. 1: Feynman Gate.

Example 1: From the Fig. 1, we can see that Feynman gate has two inputs and two outputs. So, Feynman gate is a 2×2 reversible gate as well as Fredkin gate is a 3×3 and Toffoli gate is a 3×3 reversible gate (Mamun & Hossain, 2012).

2. Garbage Output

Garbage is the output that has no use as input to other gates. Another way we can say that the output is needed to fulfill the reversibility of a reversible gate or circuit is called garbage output.

Example 2: The garbage output of Feynman gate is expressed with * in Fig. 1. In addition, Fredkin gate has one and Toffoli gate has two garbage outputs (Feynman, 1986).

3. Quantum Cost

The quantum cost of any reversible circuit is identified as the number of 1×1 and 2×2 quantum primitives, which are used to form equivalent quantum circuit (Quantum Cost Calculation in Reversible Circuits). The quantum cost of reversible Feynman gate is one, Toffoli gate is five and Double Feynman gate is two (Quantum Cost Calculation in Reversible Circuits). Actually, the quantum cost depends on using controlled-v, controlled-v+, NOT gate and CNOT gate (Feynman, 1986). Lower quantum cost is best for any reversible gate. So at present, researchers are trying to reduce the quantum cost of a reversible gate.

Example 3: The quantum cost of Feynman gate is two (Mamun & Hossain, 2012).

4. Constant Input

Constant inputs are the inputs of reversible gate or circuit that are either set to 0 or 1.

Example 4: We will get A' from the Feynman gate, if we give constant value 1 to B in Fig. 1.

5. Read Only Memory

Read-Only Memory (ROM) is a medium of data storage where data can only be read. Data is stored in ROM permanently. If the power of computer is turned OFF, the data will not be lost. ROM stores the data, which helps to start a computer.

Besides, there are some properties of read only memory as following:

1. Non-volatile: The data that is stored in ROM is not removed whether the power is ON or OFF. So, it is called non-volatile storage.
2. Security: The data is not removed or changed easily; as a result it provides security.

There are several kinds of ROM as following:

1. ROM- Read Only Memory.
2. PROM- Programmable Read Only Memory.
3. EPROM- Erasable Programmable Read Only Memory.
4. EEPROM- Electrically Erasable Programmable Memory.
5. Flash EEPROM

6. Programmable Read Only Memory (PROM)

ROM was much time-consuming and expensive when ROM chips were first created. Mainly, for this reason, the developer made a ROM that is programmable and this ROM is known as programmable read only memory or PROM (Yang, Oh, Kang, Jung, Yang, & You, 2013).

PROPOSED METHOD

Methodology is the systematic, theoretical analysis of the methods applied to a field of study. Now we discuss about decoder, proposed design of a 2 to 4 reversible decoder, proposed design of PROM, which will help to understand about our new design of RPROM.

1. Decoder

A decoder is a device that reverses the operation of encoder and it has multiple inputs and multiple outputs. The inputs and outputs follow the rule of n to 2^n . Here n is the number of inputs and 2^n is the number of outputs. If input becomes $n=1, 2, 3, \dots$, then output will be $2^1=2, 2^2=4, 2^3=8, \dots$

The binary encoded input number of a decoder is passed to ROM, which is referred to as address. The address line is presented by every signal line.

2. Proposed Design of 2 to 4 Reversible Decoder

A decoder is a circuit that changes a code into a set of signals (Aradhya, Chinmaye, & Muralidhara, 2012). In this paper, we have proposed a reversible decoder gate named ITS Decoder gate, which acts as a decoder when C and D remain constant inputs 0 and 1, respectively. The proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate is shown in Fig. 2. The quantum cost of the proposed reversible decoder is the lowest and the quantum cost is only 7. The quantum representation of the proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate is shown in Fig. 3 and the truth table is given in Table 1. There is no garbage output in ITS Decoder gate. The proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate is 12.5% better than any other existing decoder in terms of quantum cost.

Fig. 2: Proposed Reversible ITS Decoder Gate.

Fig. 3: Quantum Representation of the Proposed Reversible ITS Decoder Gate.

Table 1 shows the truth table of the proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate. We get the one-to-one mapping between input vectors and output vectors (Babu, Islam, Chowdhury, & Chowdhury, 2004) from the Table 1. P, Q, R and S of Table 1 represent the outputs of the proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate, respectively.

Table 1: Truth Table of the Proposed Reversible ITS Decoder Gate.

A	B	C	D	P	Q	R	S
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0
0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1
0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1
1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1

3. Proposed Design of RPRM

In the proposed design of RPRM, we have used the proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate, AND plane and EX-OR plane. RPRM uses decoder as input, as well as EX-OR plane and AND planes are used as output, which is shown in Fig. 4. The output of the proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate is selected as AND array plane's input terms. The output of AND plane is used into

the EX-OR plane's input. Final output of EX-OR plane shows the output of PROM. Every line of input and output is known as address line and every bit is known as word.

Fig. 4: Block Diagram of the Proposed RPRM.

RPRM and Reversible Programmable Logic Array (RPLA) have almost same architectural design. The main difference between RPRM and RPLA is: RPRM consists of an AND plane and an EX-OR plane, where AND plane is fixed and EX-OR plane is programmable; but in RPLA, both the AND plane and EX-OR plane remain programmable. It is also mentioned here that there is no existing design of RPRM. So, in this paper, we show the comparison with the existing RPLA design. A large number of equations can have for a RPRM.

To propose our new RPRM, we have used Feynman gate and MUX gates (Mitra, Jamal, & Babu). We have also proposed a new reversible gate named TI gate. Its quantum cost is five. Proposed AND plane and EX-OR plane is better than existing RPLA in terms of quantum cost, garbage outputs and number of gates (Mitra, Jamal, & Babu). Example of the multi-ESOP (Exclusive Sum Of Products) functions are $F = \{f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5\}$. In the proposed RPRM, let we have the following functions:

$$f_1 = a b' \oplus a b' c$$

$$f_2 = a c \oplus a' b' c$$

$$f_3 = a b' \oplus b c' \oplus a b' c$$

$$f_4 = a c$$

$$f_5 = a b' \oplus a c \oplus b c'$$

The input variables depend on products. In EX-OR plane, the products of function will be generated. We have established two algorithms for the proposed RPRM: one is for EX-OR plane and another is for AND plane.

The proposed 3×3 reversible TI gate has been used to get new RPRM. It has been used to reduce the number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost of AND plane as well as EX-OR plane. The quantum cost of the proposed reversible TI gate is five and garbage output is one. The proposed reversible TI gate is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Proposed Reversible TI Gate.

Table 2 shows the truth table of the proposed reversible TI gate. We get the one-to-one mapping between input vectors and output vectors (Babu, Islam, Chowdhury, & Chowdhury, 2004) from the Table 2. P, Q and R of Table 2 represent the outputs of the proposed reversible TI gate, respectively.

Table 2: Truth Table of the Proposed Reversible TI Gate.

A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	0
0	1	0	0	1	1
0	1	1	0	0	0
1	0	0	1	1	1
1	0	1	1	1	0
1	1	0	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	0	1

There exist three modes of Feynman gate, which has been used in the proposed design of RPRM: FG-1, FG-2, and FG-4, which are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Different Uses of Feynman Gate for Different Purposes.

Two modes of MUX gate: MG-5 and MG-6, which are shown in Fig. 7. In addition, one mode of TI gate: TI-7 is shown in Fig. 8. POINT is used when no gate is used to design the circuit.

Fig. 7: Two Acting Templates of MUX Gate.

Fig. 8: One Acting Template of the Proposed Reversible TI Gate.

Size of the function [*Size Of* (f_x)]: Size of the function is the number of total products that is expressed in the ESOP form.

Example 5: The number of products of f_1 is 2, f_2 is 2 and f_3 is 3. The product of functions is shown in the Table 3.

Table 3: The Product of Functions.

Functions	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5
Number of Products	2	2	3	1	3

If anyone wants, he can use more number of products and functions.

In this paper, we have proposed a new design of a RPRM. RPRM consists of an AND plane and an EX-OR plane. RPLA also consists of an AND plane and an EX-OR plane. Researchers have done many works on RPLA. Existing design shows the multi-output ESOP functions, where $F = \{f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5\}$ (Rahman, Jamal, & Babu, 2011). In the proposed design, AND plane and EX-OR plane is used for particular assuming functions. We cannot compare with any RPRM, so that we compare with existing RPLA. The proposed AND plane and EXOR plane is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: Proposed Design of AND Plane and EX-OR Plane of RPRM.

In the proposed design of RPRM, the order of output functions is related to the number of products. For EX-OR plane, the proposed algorithm is given below.

Algorithm 1: Formation of EX-OR Plane

1. **START**
 - a. TPOINT:=0 [TPOINT= Total Number of DOT]
 - b. Arrange the Output Functions According to Their Products.
2. **REDO** Step 2 for Every Output Function f_x of F.
 - a. **IF** a Single Product or All Products of a Function f_x Exits, **THEN** Use FG-2.
 - i. **ELSE** Assign Product to f_x and Use POINT
 1. TPOINT:= TPOINT+1
 - ii. **END IF**
 1. For EX-OR Operation, Use FG-4.
 - b. **END IF**
3. **END**

Theorem 1: Let the number of EX-OR operations x and y represent the number of output functions. $TPOINT$ is the number of cross points, then the minimum number Feynman gates of EX-OR plane is $x + y - TPOINT$.

Proof: If the number of EX-OR operations x , y is the number of output functions followed by $TPOINT$ is the cross point of EX-OR plane, then the total number of Feynman gates required for EX-OR plane is $x + y - TPOINT$. In EX-OR plane, the number of EX-OR operation x is 3, the number of output function y is 5 and the number of $TPOINT$ is 4. So, total number of Feynman gates of EX-OR plane is $x + y - TPOINT = 3 + 5 - 4 = 4$.

Theorem 2: If the number of product is p and the total number cross point is $TPOINT$, then the garbage output of EX-OR plane is $p - TPOINT$.

Proof: Here, $TPOINT$ is the cross point and product is p for y output functions. So, the number of garbage outputs of EX-OR plane is $p - TPOINT$. In the proposed EX-OR plane, product p is 5 and the cross point $TPOINT$ is 4. So, the number of garbage outputs of the proposed EX-OR plane is $p - TPOINT = 5 - 2 = 3$.

Algorithm 2: Formation of AND Plane

1. **START**
 1. TPOINT:=0 [Here, TPOINT is the Total Number of POINT]
2. **REDO** Step 2 to Get Every Product P_i .
 1. **IF** P_i is the First Input of f_x , **THEN**
 1. **IF** P_i is in Complementary Form, **THEN** Use FG-1
 2. **END IF**
 2. **ELSE**
 1. **IF** Input is in Copy Form, **THEN** Use FG-2
 2. **END IF**
 3. **ELSE** Use POINT and TPOINT: = TPOINT+1
 4. **END IF**
 1. **ELSE IF** P_i is in Complementary Form, **THEN** Use MG-6
 2. **END IF**
 5. **ELSE** Use MG-5
 6. **END IF**
 3. **END IF**
 4. **END IF**
3. **IF** Full Function Reads, **THEN** use TI-7
4. **END IF**
5. **END**

DISCUSSION

The comparison between the proposed and the existing designs is shown in Table 4. The achievement of the proposed reversible ITS Decoder gate is at quantum cost. The quantum cost is the lowest as compared to the existing decoders (Morrison, Lewandowski, Meana, & Ranganathan, 2011) and (Nachtigal & Ranganathan, 2011).

Table 4: Comparison between the Proposed and Existing Decoders in Terms of Quantum Cost.

Reversible Decoders	Quantum Cost
Proposed Design	7
Existing Design (Nachtigal & Ranganathan, 2011)	8
Existing Design (Morrison, Lewandowski, Meana, & Ranganathan, 2011)	10

Table 5 shows the comparison between the proposed design and the best known existing designs (Rahman, Jamal, & Babu, 2011). From Table 5, we can see that the proposed design is not fault tolerant where the existing design is fault tolerant.

Table 5: Comparison between the Proposed and Existing Designs.

Designs	Total Gates	Quantum Cost	Garbage Outputs
Proposed Design	15	38	10
Existing Design (Rahman, Jamal, & Babu, 2011)	17	55	19

The number of total gates, quantum cost and garbage outputs are lower in the proposed design as compared to the best known existing design (Rahman, Jamal, & Babu, 2011), which is given in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: Comparison between the Proposed and Existing Designs.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, our main focus is to propose a Reversible Programmable Read Only Memory (RPRM). We have also reduced the quantum cost of reversible decoder, which is the lowest cost in the literature till now. The reversible gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost have been reduced for AND plane and EX-OR plane. The 4×4 reversible decoder, AND plane and EX-OR plane are working successfully. The power and the information loss can be reduced by the proposed RPRM design.

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